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INCLUSION OF PRONUNCIATION IN ENGLISH TEXTBOOKS FOR PRIMARY EDUCATION: A MIXED-METHODS STUDY

*Inclusión de la pronunciación en los libros de texto de inglés para Educación
Primaria: Un estudio mixto*

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Abstract:

A careful look at the market for English textbooks for Primary Education in Spain reveals many gaps in the inclusion of pronunciation. Although the market is wide and varied, with books of different nature and pedagogical and methodological approaches, it can be observed that pronunciation teaching does not stand out for its treatment. In fact, it has been neglected in favour of other, more traditional skills. This study will be of a mixed nature, for which we will conduct a concurrent design using a ten-question questionnaire developed by the researcher and validated by several experts. The sample examines eight publishers, half Spanish and half international, with the presence of English textbooks in Primary Education. The main objective was to identify how different publishers treated pronunciation activities in their textbooks. Our research hypothesis was that there is a relationship between the publisher's country of origin and the treatment of pronunciation in textbooks. The results show that the place of origin of the publisher, either national or international, influences the treatment of pronunciation in the textbooks we examined.

The conclusion obtained was that international publishers tend to give greater diffusion and importance to pronunciation than national publishers, still reluctant to equate the role of pronunciation with that of other skills.

Keywords: *English textbooks; mixed study; Primary Education; pronunciation; questionnaire.*

Resumen:

Una cuidadosa mirada al mercado de libros de texto de inglés para la Educación Primaria en España revela muchas lagunas en cuanto a la inclusión de la pronunciación se refiere. A pesar de que dicho mercado es amplio y variado, existiendo libros de diferente naturaleza y enfoque pedagógico y metodológico, se observa que la enseñanza de la pronunciación no destaca por su tratamiento. De hecho, se encuentra arrinconada en favor de otras destrezas más tradicionales. Este estudio tendrá un carácter mixto para lo cual llevaremos a cabo un diseño concurrente mediante la utilización de un cuestionario de diez preguntas elaborado por el propio investigador y validado por varios expertos. La muestra examina un total de ocho editoriales, la mitad españolas y la otra mitad internacionales, con presencia de libros de texto de inglés en Educación Primaria. El objetivo principal es identificar el tratamiento que le dan las distintas editoriales a las actividades de pronunciación en sus manuales. La hipótesis de investigación que planteamos es que hay relación entre el país de origen de la editorial y el planteamiento de la pronunciación en sus manuales. Los resultados muestran que el lugar de origen de la editorial, nacional o internacional, influye en el tratamiento de la pronunciación en los libros de texto examinados. La conclusión obtenida fue que las editoriales internacionales tienden a dar mayor difusión e importancia a la pronunciación que las editoriales nacionales, aún reacias a equiparar el papel de la pronunciación con el de otras destrezas.

Palabras clave: *cuestionario; Educación Primaria; estudio mixto; libros de inglés; pronunciación.*

1. Introduction

Although pronunciation is essential for optimal oral communication and plays an important role in the social lives of learners, according to Nguyen et al. (2021), it has often been relegated to the background of English language teaching, particularly in Primary Education. Although the communicative approach has modified the objectives, English language teaching in Spain still has a literacy base in which pronunciation is often avoided in the classroom.

Quite often, teachers are unsure how to integrate pronunciation into their lessons, and they lack the methods, strategies, and training to teach them to their pupils. Consequently, teachers base their classes on the development of other skills, such as reading or writing, and often neglect pronunciation, which is a key element for good communication (Juan, 2024). In this way, we can observe a number of faults in the oral expressions of students, who still think that pronunciation is one of the most challenging aspects in foreign language acquisition. Thus, various studies have suggested that, in general, teachers feel unprepared to teach pronunciation because of their lack of knowledge or experience within English phonetics (Beltrán, 2017; Fernández, 2009).

This study examined the presence of pronunciation activities in English textbooks in Primary Education in Spain. We chose this topic because despite the importance of phonetics in English language learning, pronunciation teaching remains a pending subject in Primary Education classrooms in our country (Juan, 2024).

Despite the innovations and changes implemented in foreign language learning and the importance currently placed on the communicative approach, pronunciation has not been found in the classroom (Juan, 2024). As highlighted above, one of the reasons may be that teachers do not know how to incorporate it into their classes, and on the other hand, they do not have suitable instruments to introduce it into the classroom. Moreover, there is almost no teaching method in the market that specifically considers pronunciation development among Primary Education students but for a pair of cases (Beramendi & Cosentino, 2019).

Consequently, the general objective of this study was to determine the inclusion and treatment of pronunciation activities in some of the most widespread English textbooks in Primary Education in Spain. For this purpose, eight representative coursebooks, one from each publisher, were randomly selected for examination through a questionnaire measured on a dichotomous scale (yes/no).

1.1. Theoretical framework

Even at the risk of leaving out some important studies, we made a representative selection of the scientific production on the subject matter under study, as the theoretical framework in a mixed study tends to be broader by considering multiple approaches and perspectives to achieve an in-depth understanding of the study phenomenon.

To do so, we scrutinised the existing scientific production by Spanish authors since they examined the role of English textbooks in Primary Education in Spain. We reviewed not only articles or book chapters, but also doctoral theses, final degree projects, and master's dissertations to make it as varied as possible.

According to Asensio & Beltrán (2023), the inclusion of phonetics, rhythm, accentuation, and intonation in Royal Decree 95/2022 on 1st March, which establishes the minimum teaching standards for Primary Education in Spain following the approval of the LOMCE, and the attitudinal shift in English teaching towards a more communicative approach, is increasing the presence of pronunciation in English classrooms in Primary Education schools.

However, this has not translated into a greater inclusion of pronunciation in Primary Education textbooks. One reason for this may be that publishers have not yet had enough time to introduce all necessary modifications. Similarly, although some previous national studies have been found in the existing scientific literature on English textbooks for Primary, almost none have focused on the inclusion of pronunciation in such textbooks. Therefore, in this section, we analysed 15 previous studies on Primary Education English textbooks, focusing on the inclusion and treatment of pronunciation activities in them.

One of the first studies to be published was that of Bazo and Peñate in 1999, with the aim of analysing Primary Education English textbooks. These authors were pioneers in examining the organisation of the contents presented in the textbooks. In this sense, they stated that for the oral production of simple messages, the student was not obliged to go beyond situations of communication with the teacher and classmates that had already been worked on in class previously. Bearing in mind the year of publication of the article, although they referred to oral expressions, they did not include pronunciation in textbooks.

Another interesting article, though applied to another educational stage, was published by Jiménez in 2003, who presented the results of an evaluation of a corpus of textbooks for the teaching of English in Early Childhood Education. The author analysed 14 textbooks belonging to five publishers following an evaluation model that did not include pronunciation. As the author mentioned, “our model of analysis is inspired by the proposal of McDonough and Shaw, who recommend two phases: external evaluation and internal evaluation, in addition to a final global assessment” (Jiménez, 2003, p. 239). We observed that their comparative study was based on the analysis of the contents and suitability of the materials without dwelling on the presence of pronunciation in the textbooks.

The purpose of the study conducted by Criado and Sánchez in 2009 was to analyse whether the textbooks chosen by the authors were in line with the methodological regulations of the time. These authors were the first to examine a finite sample of textbooks, although in their case they focused on their communicative nature. Moreover, they included books belonging to various educational stages by examining only one unit, not the whole book, selected at random from each one of the textbooks: “All the activities in these units have been analysed and contrasted against the communicative feature specified” (Criado & Sánchez, 2009, p. 7).

A few years later, an article was published by Leganés and Pérez (2012), who evaluated Primary Education English textbooks from the perspective of music. The authors conducted a historical review of different teaching methods, specifying how music could help facilitate English learning by providing holistic education. Another difference with our study is that the authors developed an analysis of English textbooks from only three publishers, focusing on 3rd Primary, rather than 1st Primary as in our case. As they stated, “the aim of this study is to find out how music is used in Primary English textbooks to promote English language learning” (Leganés & Pérez, 2012, p. 116). This was the first study consulted that examined the inclusion of pronunciation. In the discussion of the results, the authors mentioned that musical activities were used to reinforce the learning of each unit, primarily vocabulary and pronunciation.

A final degree project developed by Lisbona in 2014 examined the inclusion of basic skills in Primary Education English textbooks. In this case, the author analysed four different textbooks in which the type of tasks and number of skills included

were analysed; however, pronunciation was not included among the parameters to be observed.

One year later, González (2015) published an article in which she verified the suitability of textbooks for teaching and learning English, although in her case she focused on adult education. The author selected three pre-intermediate English textbooks for adults, stating that “the main criterion for their selection lies in the representativeness of the material from the last two decades” (González, 2015, p. 346). However, her study did not consider the presence of pronunciation as a parameter to be evaluated.

In 2016, two articles based on the analysis of textbooks were published in the same journal, although only one focused on English language teaching. Malla’s article analysed the role that the selection of materials played in the teaching-learning process, focusing on the secondary stage. However, she acknowledged the inclusion of phonics: “The course should be as varied as possible, including the teaching of vocabulary, grammar, phonics, functions, and promoting the integrated use of the four skills” (Malla, 2016, p. 715). The author also emphasised the evaluation of the presentation of the skills so that there was an equitable proportion of all skills, analysing whether the skills were presented in an integrated or separated way.

A master’s dissertation in 2016 by Laorga conducted a comparative analysis of textbooks in the area of English as a foreign language, albeit at a different educational level, Early Childhood Education. The author examined seven different textbooks under a series of parameters (design, method, activities, content, assessment, and curriculum), including pronunciation, although without too much depth on this specific aspect.

An article that specifically analysed Primary Education textbooks for the English subject was published by Menescardi et al. in 2017. The authors examined five collections of English textbooks from five publishers for the third cycle of Primary Education in Spain between 2006 and 2014. However, the study only focused on analysing 1774 images related to body stereotypes without going into detail about linguistic elements, let alone pronunciation.

In 2018, we found a final degree project of similar nature to this study. Herrero compiled information on English textbooks from different periods aimed at Primary Education students to determine how their methodological principles evolved and explain the reasons for this evolution. Using qualitative methodology, the author described the evolution that textbooks have undergone in their methodology through content analysis. However, the difference with our study is that he did not only focus on the types of activities, including pronunciation, unit procedure or material, but also on the role of the teacher and students.

More recently, in 2019, Gris published an article in which he established a clear relationship between skills and activities in Primary Education textbooks, a topic that is quite close to our study. To do so, the author examined almost 2000

activities extracted from ten different textbooks frequently used for teaching English at Primary level in Spain, with the aim of examining the pedagogical nature of the activities. However, he did not focus specifically on the inclusion of pronunciation activities, but on the typology of pronunciation activities.

Another final degree project (Caviedes, 2019) focused on analysing the presence of cultural elements in English textbooks for the third year of Primary Education following a number of criteria. Furthermore, the author examined only four textbooks from different publishers, without including pronunciation, in her analysis.

A book chapter published in 2021 by Sánchez evaluated textbooks for use in Primary Education, according to a series of principles chosen by the author: learnability, utility, engaging/disposable content, thematic continuity, and objectives. The peculiarity of the study lies in the fact that four textbooks were analysed by undergraduate students, with the researcher's role collecting and analysing all the data. The study focused on the correlation between the textbook and the level of students, not on the inclusion of pronunciation activities.

Viscarolasaga's master's dissertation (2021) analysed Primary Education English textbooks using the CLIL approach. The author elaborated on a rubric where he examined general and CLIL aspects, but at no point did he include pronunciation, from four different textbooks. Perhaps this was due to the fact that these were non-language subjects taught through the foreign language, where the main focus was on content acquisition, not correct pronunciation.

Finally, we must include a doctoral thesis recently read by Guerra at the University of La Rioja in 2023. The author analysed and compared the contents of English textbooks in Primary Education, pointing out possible quantitative and qualitative differences in the lexis. Therefore, the inclusion of pronunciation in the analysed books was not considered.

2. Methodology

The review of the theoretical framework developed has shown that there is a wide variety of studies on the use of textbooks at various educational stages, although not all of them are focused on Primary Education. Few studies examined the inclusion of pronunciation in English textbooks. This study aims to clarify this situation, as it is currently an unresolved issue. Therefore, throughout this section, we develop the research design, objective and hypothesis, sample, instrument, and procedure for data collection and analysis.

2.1. Methodological design

The design is nothing more than a strategy to be implemented to achieve the research objectives. Therefore, Creswell (2021) defined mixed research as a

methodology in which the researcher brings together quantitative (closed) and qualitative (open) data, integrates or combines the two, and draws inferences that provide a broader view than either quantitative or qualitative data alone. A fundamental premise of this approach is that combining statistical trends (quantitative data) with personal experiences (qualitative data) provides a better understanding of the research problem than using either data set alone (Arias et al., 2022).

Ortega (2023) also argued that mixed research represents a natural complement to qualitative and quantitative research, recommending that the two methods be combined so that the strengths present in both are chosen and the weaknesses, which are fewer, and allow the researcher to visualise the research problem more fully, are reduced.

In our research, within the mixed method, we applied the concurrent design according to the classification made by Hernández Sampieri et al. (2018). This design allows the integration of multiple perspectives and approaches in the same research, which provides a more complete and enriching understanding of the phenomenon studied to simultaneously collect qualitative and quantitative data.

The independent variable was the selection of eight textbooks, one for each publisher. The dependent variable was the list of ten items or questions to be completed in the questionnaire. We must also bear in mind that ethical considerations are fundamental in any type of research, including mixed ones. Therefore, some key ethical considerations in conducting this research were privacy and confidentiality, data protection, transparency, and honesty (Mirza et al., 2023).

2.2. Objective, Research Question, and Hypothesis

The main objective of this study was to determine how different publishers consider pronunciation activities in their textbooks following a pattern established by the researcher. To frame the research objective, it is important in mixed research to consider the subject of the study and a combination of approaches since a crucial task in any research is defining its core objective (Thomas & Hodges, 2010). Considering this objective, we posed the following research question: Which publishers take the most account of pronunciation in textbooks? The concurrent design allowed us to collect and analyse quantitative and qualitative data to identify the factors influencing the treatment of pronunciation.

Our research hypothesis is that there is a direct relationship between the publisher's country of origin and the treatment of pronunciation in English textbooks. The concurrent approach we used allowed us to better explore the relationship between the two variables. As we subsequently conducted a normality test of the instrument, as well as its subsequent validation, it is now necessary to establish a null hypothesis and an alternative hypothesis to accept the correct hypothesis. In this case, the null hypothesis states that the data obtained have a normal distribution and the item means are equal, with no relationship between the variables. In

contrast, the alternative hypothesis specifies that the data do not have a normal distribution, the item means are not equal, and there is a relationship between the variables.

2.3. Sample

According to Hernández Sampieri et al. (2014), the population is defined as the set of all units of study. In mixed research, both population determination and sampling process are essential to guarantee the representativeness and validity of the results obtained. Population determination involves identifying the group of elements that are the object of study, based on the research objective and question posed in advance. Sampling process involved the selection of an adequate sample that represented the study population.

Considering the concurrent mixed design used, we decided to conduct mixed sampling, which involves selecting a representative sample through random sampling (a sample from each publisher) and selecting specific cases through purposive sampling (most recent publication date criteria). Therefore, we randomly selected a representative sample, according to the following criteria:

- Textbooks designed for the first year of Primary Education since methods are more clearly and gradually implemented in the first cycle. Perhaps, this is because the complexity and difficulty of the language taught are lower than in the upper levels.
- The representativeness of textbooks was a key factor in the selection process. To stick to this criterion, we collected information from the publishers and syllabi. Our sample is by necessity a convenience sample at random given the high number of textbooks in the market, so we opted to choose one textbook from each publisher considering the publication date.

However, we believe that the sample selection process is reasonably indicative of the teaching material used for Primary Education. The selected sample included, therefore, the following titles (n=8): “Be Curious” (Cambridge University Press), “I Wonder New” (Edebé), “Bright Academy Stars” (MacMillan), “All About Us Now” (Oxford University Press), “I Can Shine” (Pearson), “Go Far” (Richmond), “English for Plurilingual Schools” (SM), and “Young Star Plus” (Vicens Vives). Most of these titles were published in 2022, except for the last two titles.

We did not apply Fischer and Navarro’s (1997) formula for the selection of the sample, since the criterion was not that of inclusion, but of a representative sample at random. However, as Gómez-Nuñez et al. (2020) state, the number of participants is not linked to their representativeness but to the potential information they can offer. If we had used such a formula or the sample size for the proportion of a finite population (30), we should have examined 28 textbooks, that were clearly impossible to accomplish.

2.4. Data collection instrument

By selecting the correct research instrument, we were able to obtain the required information to accomplish the objectives we established at the beginning. In this research, the instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire defined by García as “a system of rational questions, ordered in a coherent way expressed in a simple and understandable language” (2015, p. 29).

For this study, a questionnaire was developed by the researcher. The questionnaire was designed in three distinct phases following Souza et al. (2017). In the first phase, the items to be included in the questionnaire were designed to make different decisions regarding the relationship between different questions. The initial phase included 15 items/questions.

The second phase tested the characteristics of the questionnaire and external validity of the instrument. For this purpose, validation was conducted by three experts in the field, who were asked to provide a quantitative rating on a Likert scale from 0 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) points for the following aspects: clarity of the questions, appropriateness of the terms used, relevance of the items, and pertinence of the questions. In addition, a qualitative assessment was requested from the experts to collect their input for each item, as qualitative assessments are indispensable when validating and adjusting an instrument (Bulger & Housner, 2007) as shown in figure 1.

Question	Quantitative Criteria				Qualitative Criteria
	Clarity	Appropriateness	Relevance	Pertinence	Comment
1					
2					
3					
4					
5					
6					
7					
8					
9					
10					

Figure 1. Evaluation criteria followed by experts

In the third and final phase of the questionnaire design, an analysis of the different contributions of the experts was conducted. Based on their suggestions and contributions, appropriate changes were made to the instrument, which was finally structured into ten items following the content validity ratio (CVR) model of Lawshe, a statistical method used to evaluate whether an item is necessary in a questionnaire. As a result, the questionnaire was approached in an eclectic manner to collect dichotomous data with a choice of only two answers (where Yes=1 and No=0) as follows:

Table 1.
Questionnaire.

QUESTIONS	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Does the book include a pronunciation section?								
2. Is there a pronunciation section in the table of contents?								
3. Does the teacher's book include pronunciation didactics?								
4. Does the book include pronunciation activities in each unit?								
5. Does it include pronunciation activities at the end of the book?								
6. Is pronunciation given the same importance as other skills?								
7. Does the method include extra material to work on pronunciation?								
8. Are segmental aspects worked in each unit?								
9. Are suprasegmental aspects worked in each unit?								
10. Are pronunciation activities included in the exams?								

To prevent the possible negative effects of the questionnaire application, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used to check the internal consistency of the questionnaire, which yielded a value of 0.69. A value of 0.69 means that the instrument is highly reliable, so we can say that the questionnaire has a high internal consistency and high reliability, and its measurements are stable and consistent. In the following table, we check the reliability of the questionnaire.

Table 2.
Questionnaire Reliability

Number items	Sum of item variance	Total instrument variance	Cronbach's alpha coefficient
10	0.84375	2.25	0.69444

2.5. Data collection procedure

The procedure for data collection consisted of three phases according to Souza et al. (2017): exploratory, fieldwork, and information processing. The exploratory phase is preliminary research conducted to clarify the research procedure to constitute the fieldwork. In this phase, we delimited the objective of our research and developed a theoretical and methodological study. Furthermore, we chose the instrument to use and the sample to be examined.

The second phase was based entirely on available fieldwork. Here, we put the theoretical construction elaborated in the previous phase into practice, with the

necessary time for data collection. The second phase was conducted by completing the questionnaire using data from eight textbooks chosen at random. For this purpose, we created a template to enter the data obtained from each publisher, and then transferred it to an Excel spreadsheet.

Finally, the third phase concerned the evaluation, understanding, and interpretation of the empirical data, articulated with the theory on which we based our study. This last phase was conducted after obtaining all data. In this phase, we conducted a descriptive analysis of the variables expressed in terms of frequency.

2.6. Data collection analysis

The data analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel, a statistical data processing software offered by Microsoft. Following Mendoza & Ramírez (2020), the procedure followed was to prepare an Excel spreadsheet, enter the data from each publisher, and then process the data statistically. For our study, we used descriptive statistics to determine the means and standard deviations.

To verify which hypothesis was valid (null or alternative), a normality test of the instrument was conducted. For this purpose, we used first the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test, which allowed us to measure the degree of agreement between the distribution of the data set and the specific theoretical distribution. After this test, the calculated Kolmogorov-Smirnov value (Ks c-value) was 0.3252, while the Kolmogorov-Smirnov table value (Ks t-value) which reflects the maximum permissible error, was 0.2869 with a standard deviation of 1.6035, and a p-value of 0.0159. Since the Ks c-value was greater than the Ks t-value, and the p-value lower than the degree of significance, we had to reject the null hypothesis because the data did not have a normal distribution and use a non-parametric test.

These data were also corroborated by the Ryan-Joiner test. With the same standard deviation of 1.6035 and a p-value of 0.0135, the calculated Ryan Joiner value (RJ c-value) was 0.8363 and the Ryan Joiner table value (RJ t-value) was 0.9029. In this case, since the RJ c-value was lower than the RJ t-value, and the p-value lower than the degree of significance, we again had to reject the null hypothesis. The degree of significance was set at 0.05 in both tests. Therefore, our research hypothesis was valid, there is a relationship between the publisher's country of origin and the treatment of pronunciation in their textbooks since the data obtained do not have a normal distribution.

Table 3.
Kolmogorov-Smirnov & Ryan-Joiner tests

Value	t-value	p-value	Test
0.3252	0.2869	0.0159	Kolmogorov-Smirnov
0.8363	0.9029	0.0135	Ryan-Joiner

Second, to perform an inferential analysis and verify the differences between the eight publishers, we applied the coefficient of variation between the different items. The following table shows the variance of each item and the coefficient of variation (CV) obtained for the whole instrument:

Table 4.
Coefficient of variation

Item 1	Item 2	Item 3	Item 4	Item 5	Item 6	Item 7	Item 8	Item 9	Item 10	CV
0	0.109375	0.25	0	0	0.25	0.234375	0	0	0	0.904534

Finally, as the p-value obtained in the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Ryan-Joiner normality tests was lower than the degree of significance (0.05), we used a non-parametric test to further analyse the results. Therefore, we conducted an inferential analysis by means of the Kruskal-Wallis test, a rank-based test that can be used to test for statistically differences between the items or questions.

3. Results

The results derived from the analysis of the questionnaire used for the research are presented analysing each question separately. For each question, beyond the quantitative data, we also focused on the conclusions drawn regarding the treatment given to pronunciation by each publisher. The eight publishers examined were those who currently have English books for Primary Education, being four Spanish (Edebé, Richmond, SM, and Vicens Vives) and four international (Cambridge, Oxford, MacMillan, and Pearson).

To conduct the analysis of the material, we considered the whole package, which included not only the pupils' books, but also all the material available to the teacher. We should also observe that we did not infringe on copyright in any way, as we did not reproduce the books in whole or in part, and the analysis was developed strictly for research purposes.

Then, we introduced a cluster analysis in which we started with the overall results first, and then focused on the results for each item separately. A checklist was designed to produce a score for the analysis of each publisher, where the scale used to evaluate the dichotomous questions was 0-1, where 0=No and 1=Yes.

Starting with the overall questionnaire results, the researcher conducted a Kruskal-Wallis test of the ten questions and the results of the eight publishers for each question. The Kruskal-Wallis H-test is a non-parametric rank-based test that can be used to test whether there are statistically relevant differences between groups of an independent variable on an ordinal or continuous dependent variable. It is a generalisation of the Wilcoxon rank sum test, allowing more than two samples to be compared to determine whether the results of a test are significant in rejecting the

null hypothesis or accepting the alternative hypothesis. The null hypothesis stated that there was a normal distribution of data, with the means being equal for each question. On the other hand, the alternative hypothesis stated that means were different for each question, as we presume. In the following table, we check the results of the Kruskal-Wallis test.

Table 5.
Kruskal-Wallis Test

Question	Total	Sum	Error	Deviation	Sum of Ranks	Ranks Squared
1	8	8	0	0	468	27378
2	8	7	0.125	0.35355339	428	22898
3	8	4	0.18898224	0.53452248	308	11858
4	8	8	0	0	468	27378
5	8	0	0	0	148	2738
6	8	4	0.18898224	0.53452248	308	11858
7	8	5	0.18298126	0.51754917	348	15138
8	8	8	0	0	468	27378
9	8	0	0	0	148	2738
10	8	0	0	0	148	2738

Likewise, this method also allows the comparison of means to determine whether there is a difference between pairs. If the calculated H-value is greater than the critical value, there is a significant difference between the pairs, which validates the alternative hypothesis when not all the mean scores are equal. Since the calculated H-value was 38.6666667 and the critical value 16.9189776, there is a difference in the treatment of pronunciation between publishers according to their place of origin, as stated in our research hypothesis. Other relevant values obtained in the test are the sum of ranks, 3240, and the sum of ranks squared, 152100.

Moving into the analysis of each question separately, the first question asked whether the book included a pronunciation section. This was one of the questions in the questionnaire in which the response was affirmative from all eight publishers as shown in the table.

Table 6.
Question 1 Statistical Differences

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Mean	1	0.875	0.5	1	0	0.5	0.625	1	0	0
Sample difference	-	0.125	0.5	0	1	0.5	0.375	0	1	1
Result	-	<	>	<	>	>	<	<	>	>
Evidence	5 significant differences, 4 non-significant differences									

The second item asked whether there was a pronunciation section in the table of contents. For almost all publishers, regardless of their origin, the answer was yes, with the exception of the Spanish publisher, Edebé, for which the answer was no. In the following table, we check the results for the second question.

Table 7.
Question 2 Statistical Differences

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Mean	1	0.875	0.5	1	0	0.5	0.625	1	0	0
Sample difference	0.125	-	0.375	0.125	0.875	0.375	0.25	0.125	0.875	0.875
Result	<	-	<	<	>	<	<	<	>	>
Evidence	3 significant differences, 6 non-significant differences									

The third question asked whether the teacher's book included didactics pronunciation. This was one of the items where we could see a difference in the answers depending on the origin of the publisher. In this case, the answer was affirmative for the four international publishers but negative for the four national publishers.

Table 8.
Question 3 Statistical Differences

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Mean	1	0.875	0.5	1	0	0.5	0.625	1	0	0
Sample difference	0.5	0.375	-	0.5	0.25	0	0.125	0.5	0.5	0.5
Result	>	<	-	>	>	<	<	>	>	>
Evidence	6 significant differences, 3 non-significant differences									

The fourth question was another in which all publishers agreed on the answer. When asked whether the book included pronunciation activities in each unit, the answer was affirmative for all publishers, although there was a noticeable difference. In the national publishers, inclusion was tokenistic, whereas international publishers included more pronunciation activities.

Table 9.
Question 4 Statistical Differences

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Mean	1	0.875	0.5	1	0	0.5	0.625	1	0	0
Sample difference	0	0.125	0.5	-	1	0.5	0.375	0	0.5	0.5
Result	<	<	>	-	>	>	<	<	>	>
Evidence	5 significant differences, 4 non-significant differences									

For the fifth question, the book included pronunciation activities at the end, we obtained the same answer from all publishers, although in this case, it was a negative one. Pronunciation activities were not included at the end of the book in any of the eight cases, regardless of the publisher's origin.

Table 10.
Question 5 Statistical Differences

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Mean	1	0.875	0.5	1	0	0.5	0.625	1	0	0
Sample difference	1	0.875	0.5	1	-	0.5	0.625	1	0	0
Result	>	>	>	>	-	>	>	>	<	<
Evidence	7 significant differences, 2 non-significant differences									

The sixth question asked whether pronunciation was given the same importance as other skills. This item reflected the division between the national and

international publishers. While none of the Spanish publishers gave the same importance to pronunciation as other skills, the presence of pronunciation was more balanced among the international publishers.

Table 11.
Question 6 Statistical Differences

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Mean	1	0.875	0.5	1	0	0.5	0.625	1	0	0
Sample difference	0.5	0.375	0	0.5	0.5	-	0.125	0.5	0.5	0.5
Result	>	<	<	>	>	-	<	>	>	>
Evidence	6 significant differences, 3 non-significant differences									

For the seventh question, we obtained an unexpected result. To the question of whether the method included extra material to work on pronunciation, we obtained a positive response from the four international publishers, as expected, but one of the national publishers (Edebé) also included it in its manual. By contrast, the other three national publishers did not.

Table 12.
Question 7 Statistical Differences

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Mean	1	0.875	0.5	1	0	0.5	0.625	1	0	0
Sample difference	0.375	0.25	0.125	0.375	0.625	0.125	-	0.375	0.625	0.625
Result	<	<	<	<	>	<	-	<	>	>
Evidence	3 significant differences, 6 non-significant differences									

The eighth question asked whether segmental aspects were worked in each textbook unit. We obtained a positive response from all publishers, although, along with the fourth question, the treatment was uneven. Although the national publishers worked on the segmental aspects, this was done in an oblique way, which was not the case with international publishers.

Table 13.
Question 8 Statistical Differences

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Mean	1	0.875	0.5	1	0	0.5	0.625	1	0	0
Sample difference	0	0.125	0.5	0	1	0.5	0.375	-	1	1
Result	<	<	>	<	>	>	<	-	>	>
Evidence	5 significant differences, 4 non-significant differences									

Finally, we obtained the same results for the last two questions. For both the ninth question, suprasegmental aspects were worked in each unit, and for the tenth question, pronunciation activities were included in the examinations, the answer was negative in both questions for all publishers as seen in the following tables.

Table 14.
Question 9 Statistical Differences

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Mean	1	0.875	0.5	1	0	0.5	0.625	1	0	0
Sample difference	1	0.875	0.5	1	0	0.5	0.625	1	-	0
Result	>	>	>	>	<	>	>	>	-	<
Evidence	7 significant differences, 2 non-significant differences									

Table 15.
Question 10 Statistical Differences

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Mean	1	0.875	0.5	1	0	0.5	0.625	1	0	0
Sample difference	1	0.875	0.5	1	0	0.5	0.625	1	0	-
Result	>	>	>	>	<	>	>	>	<	-
Evidence	7 significant differences, 2 non-significant differences									

4. Discussion of Results

After validated the ten items of the questionnaire, following the indications of the three experts, and applying the content value ratio (CVR) of Lawshe's model based on the experts' assessments, and after filling in the data from the textbooks of the eight publishers, this section presents the analysis of the results obtained.

When evaluating a textbook, a distinction has traditionally been made between predictive and prospective evaluations. The former aimed to evaluate teaching materials *a priori* to determine whether they were fit for the purpose. On the other hand, prospective evaluation was conducted after the materials had been used to assess their suitability for the specific experience of the teaching-learning process.

However, since the objective of our study was to determine how publishers considered pronunciation activities in their textbooks not if they were fit, we only applied a predictive evaluation, because the materials have not been used in the Primary Education classroom. Therefore, we limited to collecting data from the eight publishers based on our own direct participant observations from the questionnaire.

The findings of this study confirm our research hypothesis. The place of origin of the publisher, either national or international, influences the treatment of pronunciation in the textbooks examined. Not only did we examine the inclusion of pronunciation activities in the textbooks, but also, and more specifically, the importance given to it and its treatment in the method. Almost all the questions in the questionnaire showed significant differences between them in the statistical analysis, as we see in the figure.

Figure 2. Significant vs. Non-significant differences

Similarly, from a descriptive point of view, all textbooks included a pronunciation section in each unit where segmental aspects (vowels or consonants) were used, whereas none of them included pronunciation activities at the end of the book, nor did they work on suprasegmental aspects (stress, rhythm, intonation). This last factor may be justified in the educational stage we are at, where attention is not usually paid to the suprasegmental aspects, which are more typical of Secondary Education.

However, the difference between publishers lies in the remaining questions in the questionnaire. These questions denoted the difference in treatment according to the origin of the publisher, since international publishers tend to give greater diffusion and importance to pronunciation than national publishers, still reluctant to equate the role of pronunciation with that of other skills.

This is clearly seen in questions that focus specifically on the treatment of pronunciation rather than its inclusion. Thus, for example, when we asked whether the teacher's book included didactics on pronunciation, we found that all international publishers did. In contrast, none of the national publishers did so. The same data were obtained when we asked whether the book gave the same importance to pronunciation as the other skills: all international publishers did, but none of the national publishers did.

With regard to the method, the data can be extrapolated if we wanted to know whether the method included extra material to work on pronunciation, or whether it included pronunciation activities in the proposed exams. In all these cases, the results were identical: all the international publishers included them, but none of the national publishers did so. Therefore, the publisher's origin constitutes a differential variable in the treatment of pronunciation in textbooks.

To further triangulate the validity and reliability of this study, we compared our results with those of previous studies. After examining eight Primary Education textbooks from eight different publishers, this study found that the publisher's origin, national or international, affected the treatment given to the inclusion of pronunciation in the method.

Gris' study shared some items with ours in determining the importance given to pronunciation in books, as well as the inclusion of pronunciation activities in

them. The author classified pronunciation activities according to their cognitive components as explicit, implicit, or mixed. The difference with our study was that he did not focus on a single primary school year, but examined the whole stage, and pronunciation activities were not the main focus of the study. The author concluded that Primary Education English teachers should not ignore the idiosyncratic characteristics of different types of activities.

Laorga's study also considered the inclusion of pronunciation activities in textbooks, but not exclusively. Pronunciation was one of the parameters analysed alongside the design, method, content, and assessment. Moreover, by analysing a sample size similar to ours, the author focused on the Early Childhood Education stage. Nevertheless, the author acknowledged that the emphasis on phonics was relevant, as it supported children's future pronunciation, one of the foundations for speaking the language correctly. Besides, the inclusion of pronunciation activities was an item that our study also shared with Malla's, although in her case, she limited the establishment of a series of appropriate criteria for the correct selection of textbooks, especially for the Secondary Education stage.

Finally, another element of our questionnaire, which asked whether suprasegmental aspects were worked on in textbooks, was related to the study by Leganés, who established the relationship between music and English learning. According to her, music enhanced and accelerated the learning of English by bringing together both segmental and suprasegmental aspects. Among her conclusions, Leganés recognised that when children sang a song to learn the English alphabet, they were not only memorising words but also singing a melody, making use of such aspects.

5. Conclusions

Several significant conclusions can be drawn from the review conducted in the theoretical framework. First, most of the publications focused on the stage of Primary Education, the stage our research is focused on, although five examined other educational stages. Second, over half of the publications consulted corresponded to articles or book chapters in scientific journals, while the rest corresponded to master's dissertations, final degree projects, or doctoral theses. Finally, we found that only four studies paid attention to pronunciation, although none focused specifically on its inclusion in textbooks. This fact lends validity to our study because of its originality, among other aspects.

In our study, we established the objective of determining how different publishers considered the treatment of pronunciation activities in their textbooks. To answer this objective, we chose a random sample of eight textbooks from different publishers. The answer to this objective came with the establishment of our research question, where we examined how publishers included pronunciation in their textbooks, stating our research hypothesis that there was a direct relationship

between the publisher's country of origin and the treatment given to the inclusion of pronunciation in their textbooks.

To conduct this research, we applied a concurrent design within the mixed method that allowed us to bring together various perspectives and approaches to fully determine the main factors that influence the treatment of pronunciation. We also chose a mixed sample type, in which the final sample was randomly selected.

The instrument used was a questionnaire with ten dichotomous questions (YES=1 and NO=0), developed by the researcher after external validity by three experts following Lawshe's content validity ratio model. The internal consistency of the questionnaire was also tested after obtaining Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which showed the high consistency of the instrument with descriptive data.

Subsequent analysis of the data using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test led us to conduct a non-parametric statistical test. The tool selected was the Kruskal-Wallis test (H-value), which yielded sufficient data to reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative. This analysis helped demonstrate that the hypothesis was certain, the publisher's country of origin made a difference in the treatment and inclusion of pronunciation in the textbook.

The possible limitations of this study are mainly twofold. On the one hand, in the analysis of the theoretical framework, we limited to an examination of studies published by Spanish researchers that affected English textbooks in Primary Education in Spain. In the future, this approach can be extended to a wider range of studies worldwide. On the other hand, due to spatial limitations, the representative sample of English textbooks was limited to eight textbooks out of the 30 currently available on the market. If we applied the sample size for the proportion of a finite population, we would have to analyse 28 books, which is unfeasible for a unique study. Therefore, a larger sample of books should be further examined to corroborate our hypothesis.

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